

GENERALIZED IIR POLYNOMIAL PREDICTIVE FILTERS

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Abstract - The transfer functions of all polynomial predictors are derived. Previously proposed IIR polynomial predictive filters based on the feedback extension of FIR predictors are shown to be a special case of this general class.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polynomial predictors refer to linear filters capable of unbiased extrapolation of polynomial signals. A motivation for polynomial predictors is that polynomial signal models are useful in several applications, e.g. control systems [1], signal smoothing [2] and noise reduction [3].

Recursive predictor structures and iterative algorithms for their optimization have been proposed in [4]. These are based on augmenting a FIR predictor by adding the delayed output of the filter to the input, resulting in unbiased estimation of polynomial signals while adding more degrees of freedom to the filter.

In this paper, we show that the feedback extension method is a special case of a more general class of predictive IIR filters by deriving the possible transfer function of any stable IIR predictive filter.

2. TRANSFER FUNCTIONS OF IIR POLYNOMIAL PREDICTORS

In this section we formulate the characteristics of the responses of general IIR polynomial predictors. We say that a filter with impulse response $h(n)$ is a polynomial predictor of order L if the filter predicts any polynomial of order at most L one step ahead, i.e. if

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (n-k)^{\ell} h(k) = (n+1)^{\ell}, \quad (1)$$

for any n and $\ell \leq L$. In equation (1) and elsewhere, the convention $0^0 = 1$ is used.

Theorem. *Let $h(n)$ be the impulse response of a causal and stable IIR filter and let $H(z)$ be the z -transform of $h(n)$. For any integer $L \geq 0$, $H(z)$ is a polynomial predictor of degree L if and only if $1 + (1 - z^{-1})H(z)$ is a polynomial predictor of degree $L + 1$.*

Proof. First, we will determine a convenient characterization of the impulse responses of polynomial predictors. Applying the binomial formula in equation (1), we get

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{m} n^m \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell-m} h(k) = \sum_{m=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{m} n^m. \quad (2)$$

This is true for all n if and only if

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell-m} h(k) = 1,$$

because the two sides of equation (2) represent polynomials of order ℓ which obtain the same values for $\ell + 1$ different points (in fact, infinitely many), so that their coefficients must be equal.

Using this characterization and by taking inverse z -transforms, the claim of the theorem can be restated as

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell} h(k) = 1, \ell = 0, 1, \dots, L$$

if and only if

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell} \delta(k) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell} h(k) - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell} h(k-1) = 1, \quad (3)$$

for $\ell = 0, 1, \dots, L + 1$, and where $\delta(k)$ denotes the discrete impulse signal. Each sum is convergent because $h(n)$ decays exponentially since it is the impulse response of a stable IIR filter. The first term in (3) is

1 if $\ell = 0$ and 0 if $\ell > 0$. The final term in (3) can be written as

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{m} (-1)^{\ell-m} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^m h(k). \quad (4)$$

If

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell} h(k) = 1, \ell = 0, 1, \dots, L,$$

then for $\ell = 1, \dots, L$, equation (4) simplifies to

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{m} (-1)^{\ell-m} = (-1+1)^{\ell} = 0$$

and for $\ell = 0$, it equals 1. Thus, for $\ell = 0, 1, \dots, L$, the first and third terms in (3) cancel out, and we are left with

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell} h(k) = 1.$$

For $\ell = L + 1$, the final term in (3) is

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m=0}^{L+1} \binom{L+1}{m} (-1)^{L+1-m} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^m h(k) \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^L \binom{L+1}{m} (-1)^{L+1-m} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{L+1} h(k) \\ &= -1 + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{L+1} h(k). \end{aligned}$$

Using this in equation (3), we find that

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell} (\delta(k) + h(k) - h(k-1)) = 1, \ell = 0, 1, \dots, L+1, \quad (5)$$

so that $1 + (1 - z^{-1})H(z)$ is a polynomial predictor of order $L + 1$.

For the converse, assume that (5) holds. For $\ell = 1$, using (4), this reduces to

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^0 h(k) = 1.$$

Evaluated at $\ell + 1 \leq L + 1$ and using the fact that $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell} h(k) = 1$ for $0, 1, \dots, \ell - 1$, (5) equals

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_{m=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell+1}{m} (-1)^{\ell+1-m} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^m h(k) \\ &= (\ell+1) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell} h(k) - \sum_{m=0}^{\ell-1} \binom{\ell+1}{m} (-1)^{\ell+1-m} \\ &= 1, \end{aligned}$$

so that

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-k)^{\ell} h(k) = 1,$$

which completes the proof.

Next we derive the transfer functions of all stable IIR polynomial predictors of order 0. Let

$$H(z) = \frac{C(z)}{A(z)}$$

be such a predictor. As shown above, this means that

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} h(k) = H(1) = \frac{C(1)}{A(1)} = 1.$$

Define

$$B(z) = \frac{C(z) - A(z)}{1 - z^{-1}},$$

which is a polynomial, since $C(z) - A(z)$ has a zero at $z = 1$. Now we have

$$1 + (1 - z^{-1}) \frac{B(z)}{A(z)} = \frac{C(z)}{A(z)}.$$

Thus any stable IIR predictor of order 0 can be written as

$$1 + (1 - z^{-1}) \frac{B(z)}{A(z)}. \quad (6)$$

Conversely, for any choice of $B(z)$ and any $A(z)$ with zeros inside the unit circle, (6) evaluated at $z = 1$ is equal to 1, since $A(1) \neq 0$. Thus the polynomial predictive IIR filters of order 0 are given by (6) with $\frac{B(z)}{A(z)}$ stable.

Now by the above theorem, polynomial predictors of order 1 are exactly of the form

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 + (1 - z^{-1}) \left(1 + (1 - z^{-1}) \frac{B(z)}{A(z)} \right) \\ &= 1 + (1 - z^{-1}) + (1 - z^{-1})^2 \frac{B(z)}{A(z)} \end{aligned}$$

and applying the theorem repeatedly we find that the transfer functions of IIR polynomial predictors of order L are

$$1 + (1 - z^{-1}) + \dots + (1 - z^{-1})^L + (1 - z^{-1})^{L+1} \frac{B(z)}{A(z)}, \quad (7)$$

where $B(z)$ and $A(z)$ are arbitrary except that the roots of $A(z)$ must have absolute value less than 1. Fig. 1 shows this general structure.

Figure 1: General polynomial predictor structure for ramp signals. For higher polynomial orders, the nesting in the structure is correspondingly deeper.

3. AUGMENTED FIR STRUCTURES AS IIR POLYNOMIAL PREDICTORS

In this section we will show that the augmented FIR structure in [4] is a special case of the general transfer function derived in the preceding section. In the augmented FIR structure the denominator order cannot exceed the numerator order by more than 1 and thus cannot include all of the IIR predictors given by (7). However, even some predictors with appropriate numerator and denominator orders are missed, which can be seen as follows.

Consider the augmented FIR in Fig. 2 with $L = 0$, i.e. a level predictor, so that

$$h_0 = h_1 = h_2 = h_3 = \frac{1}{4}.$$

Now if we fix the feedback coefficients,

$$b_0 = \frac{1}{2}, b_1 = b_2 = b_3 = 0,$$

say, the augmented FIR will have the transfer function

$$\frac{\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{8}z^{-1} + \frac{1}{8}z^{-2} + \frac{1}{8}z^{-3}}{1 - \frac{1}{2}z^{-1}}.$$

Now consider the transfer function

$$\frac{1 - \frac{1}{2}z^{-1} + (1 - z^{-1})(c_0 + c_1z^{-1} + c_2z^{-2})}{1 - \frac{1}{2}z^{-1}}, \quad (8)$$

which is a level predictor for any choice of c_0, c_1, c_2 . Specifically, if we choose

$$c_0 = -\frac{7}{8}, c_1 = -\frac{1}{4}, c_2 = -\frac{1}{8},$$

the transfer function will be equal to the augmented FIR above. However, for other choices of c_0, c_1, c_2 , the transfer function (8) cannot be represented as an augmented FIR, even though the numerator and denominator orders do not prevent this. This is because

Figure 2: Augmented FIR structure.

the feedforward coefficients are fixed and changing the feedback coefficients would change the denominator.

The requirement that the underlying FIR predictor in the augmented FIR structure be specifically the Heinonen-Neuvo predictor is not necessary and we may use any FIR predictor [5] in its place without destroying the predictive capabilities of the augmented structure. In this case it is unclear whether any IIR predictor with appropriate numerator and denominator orders can be represented as an augmented FIR.

In [6] it is claimed that IIR predictors are better able to track fast changes in the signal than FIR predictors because of the short length of the constituent filters. This is not strictly true, however, since the length of the impulse response does not depend on the window length in IIR filters. In the example considered in [6], the conclusion seems to be correct due to the better magnitude response of the IIR predictor and the fact that the impulse response of the IIR filter is more concentrated than that of the FIR filter.

4. DESIGN EXAMPLE OF AN OPTIMAL LOW-ORDER IIR POLYNOMIAL PREDICTOR

In this section we consider the design of the minimum noise-gain IIR polynomial predictor for first-order polynomials, with numerator and denominator orders 5 and

2, respectively. The optimization of IIR predictors is in general a difficult optimization problem and requires iterative methods [6].

For low-order predictors, however, a grid search of the denominator coefficients is feasible. For a given denominator $A(z)$, we can solve for the optimal numerator in the following manner. The transfer function of the predictor is

$$2 - z^{-1} + \frac{(1 - z^{-1})^2(r_0 + r_1z^{-1} + r_2z^{-2} + r_3z^{-3})}{A(z)}$$

and the truncated impulse response is

$$\mathbf{f} + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{r},$$

where $\mathbf{f}$ is the $N \times 1$ vector of impulse response coefficients of $2 - z^{-1}$, $\mathbf{H}$ is the $N \times 4$ convolution matrix of the filter $\frac{(1-z^{-1})^2}{A(z)}$,

$$\mathbf{r} = \begin{bmatrix} r_0 \\ r_1 \\ r_2 \\ r_3 \end{bmatrix},$$

and N is the length of the truncation. We don't lose too much precision in the truncation of the responses if N is large since $\frac{1}{A(z)}$ is stable. Now minimizing the noise gain is equivalent to minimizing the vector norm

$$\|\mathbf{f} + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{r}\|^2.$$

From standard matrix theory, the solution to this is

$$\mathbf{r} = -(\mathbf{H}^T\mathbf{H})^{-1}\mathbf{H}^T\mathbf{f}. \quad (9)$$

For the denominator, we represent the filter using the reflection coefficients [7] of the lattice structure so that we can easily ensure the stability of the filter. A grid search is done on the reflection coefficient space

$$[-0.98, 0.98] \times [-0.98, 0.98].$$

For each denominator, we determine the optimal numerator from equation (9). A new grid search is then performed around the best denominator reflection coefficients found in the first stage, and this procedure is iterated.

The resulting predictor has the transfer function

$$\frac{1.89 - 1.27z^{-1} + 0.02z^{-2} + 0.01z^{-3} + 0.80z^{-4} - 1.11z^{-5}}{10(1 - 1.6096z^{-1} + 0.6424z^{-2})}$$

The impulse and magnitude responses are shown in Fig. 3. The noise gain of the filter is 0.2010, which is better than the optimal FIR filter of length 21. We note that the filter has a pole at the maximum allowed radius on the real line.

Figure 3: Minimum noise gain ramp IIR predictor with numerator degree 5 and denominator degree 2.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The transfer functions of all IIR polynomial predictive filters were derived and shown to yield a predictor class more general than those considered earlier. Due to the increased degrees of freedom, this class is likely to give better results than the augmented FIR structure e.g. when minimizing the noise gain of predictors.

6. REFERENCES

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